

1 Supplement 1 (extended methods, data, and figures)
2 *The extended ‘common cause’: causal links between punctuated*
3 *evolution and sedimentary processes*

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Grid Scale

27 **Table S 1- Specimens used for analysis of aperture shape.** AMNH=American
 28 Museum of Natural History; IP= Invertebrate Paleontology; IZ=Invertebrate Zoology;
 29 MCZ=Museum of Comparative Zoology, Harvard University; YPM=Yale Peabody Museum,
 30 Yale University.

Taxon	Catalog Number	Type	ID
<i>P. bermudensis bermudensis</i>	YPM IZ 104396	Extant	7
<i>P. bermudensis fasolti</i>	MCZ 196560	Fossil	1
<i>P. bermudensis fasolti</i>	YPM IP 103287	Fossil	2
<i>P. bermudensis sieglindae</i>	YPM IP 117788	Fossil	5
<i>P. bermudensis zonatus</i>	MCZ 196565	Fossil	8
<i>P. bermudensis zonatus</i>	YPM IP 103335	Fossil	3
<i>P. bermudensis zonatus</i>	YPM IP 103392	Fossil	9
<i>P. bermudensis zonatus</i>	YPM IP 117761	Fossil	4
<i>P. bermudensis zonatus</i>	YPM IP 117831	Fossil	6
<i>P. bermudensis zonatus</i>	YPM IP 544103	Fossil	10
<i>P. bermudensis zonatus</i>	YPM IP 544163	Fossil	11
<i>P. circumfirmatus</i>	YPM IP 544102	Fossil	18
<i>P. circumfirmatus acutissimus</i>	YPM IP 117832	Fossil	16
<i>P. circumfirmatus acutissimus</i>	YPM IP 117890	Fossil	17
<i>P. circumfirmatus circumfirmatus</i>	AMNH IZ 45174	Extant	12
<i>P. circumfirmatus circumfirmatus</i>	YPM IP 103332	Fossil	14
<i>P. circumfirmatus circumfirmatus</i>	YPM IP 103391	Fossil	15
<i>P. circumfirmatus discrepans</i>	YPM IP 103286	Fossil	13
<i>P. cupula cupula</i>	YPM IP 544162	Fossil	19
<i>P. cupula multispira</i>	YPM IP 117958	Fossil	20
<i>P. cupula triangularis</i>	MCZ 196561	Fossil	21
<i>P. nelsoni conoides</i>	YPM IP 102701	Fossil	22
<i>P. nelsoni nelsoni</i>	MCZ 196559	Fossil	23
<i>P. nelsoni nelsoni</i>	YPM IP 102646	Fossil	24
<i>P. reinianus</i>	AMNH IZ 45173	Extant	25
<i>P. reinianus</i>	MCZ 196563	Fossil	26
<i>P. reinianus</i>	MCZ 196567	Fossil	27
<i>P. reinianus</i>	YPM IP 103252	Fossil	28
<i>P. reinianus</i>	YPM IP 119183	Fossil	29
<i>P. reinianus</i>	YPM IP 119184	Fossil	30
<i>P. reinianus</i>	YPM IP 544267	Fossil	31

31 Aperture shape in the Raup models was parameterized with shape coordinates derived
32 from geometric morphometric analysis of the apertures of extant and fossil *Poecilozonites*
33 from Bermuda. Individual specimens were selected to represent the full range of realized
34 aperture shapes (**Table S1**).

35

36 Each specimen was scanned with x-ray microtomography at either the American Museum
37 of Natural History for AMNH specimens or the University of Minnesota Department of
38 Earth and Environmental Sciences for all other specimens. The shells were segmented and
39 meshed in 3D Slicer v. 5.0.2 (Fedorov et al. 2012). The aperture was also traced using 3D
40 Slicer and an initial set of semilandmark points placed along it. The initial semilandmarks
41 were then imported into *Morphometrics for Mathematica* v. 12.4 (Polly 2022), where they
42 were reprocessed into configurations of 40 equally spaced 3D landmarks, Procrustes
43 superimposed, and projected into a principal components morphospace (Rohlf and Slice
44 1990; Bookstein 1991; Dryden & Mardia 1998; Polly and Motz 2016). The superimposed
45 semilandmarks are shown in **Fig. S2** and the semilandmark configuration, the ordination
46 of the specimens on the first two principal component (PC) axes, and shape models
47 illustrating the variation explained by PC 1 & 2 are illustrated in **Fig. S3**.

48

49 **Figure S 2-Procrustes superimposed landmarks.** 40 superimposed aperture
50 semilandmarks from 32 specimens of *Poecilozonites* (Table S1). Each semilandmark label
51 is positioned on its mean and the dotted lines connect each semilandmark to the aperture
52 centroid.

53

54 **Figure S 3-Geometric morphometric analysis.** First two dimensions of the principal
 55 components (PC) morphospace for *Poecilozonites* apertures. The inset shows
 56 semilandmarks in place on a *P. bermudensis zonatus* specimen. Specimens are labeled by
 57 ID from Table S1.

58 The first two dimensions of the morphospace were used as shape variables in the
 59 visualizations produced from computational model. In the model, drift processes were
 60 simulated in three shell coiling parameters (W, T, D) and two shape parameters (S_1 , S_2) (see
 61 main text for details). The simulations based on those parameters are completely
 62 independent of the morphometric results obtained here (i.e., the computation models treat
 63 the traits as simple continuous variables that evolve by Brownian motion and could
 64 represent any unbounded trait). The outcomes of the computational model were
 65 transformed into virtual snail shells for visual comparison. For aperture shape parameter,
 66 the set of S_1 and S_2 parameters were scaled so that their variances equaled the variances of
 67 PC 1 & 2 of the morphospace and multiplied by the inverse of the PC eigenvector matrix to
 68 produce shape models (c.f., Polly and Motz 2016).

69 The eigenvalues (variances) of the first two PCs were 0.0024 and 0.00092 respectively.

70 Because the shape analysis was used only for visualization and is therefore tangential to
 71 the core results presented in this paper, the microCT scans have not yet been published.
 72 They will be published later through *MorphoSource* (<https://www.morphosource.org>) as part
 73 of a larger empirical study on *Poecilozonites*. The semilandmark dataset used here is
 74 included as a separate TPS file for anyone wishing to replication these results
 75 **(Supplement 4)**.

Evolutionary rate analysis

77

78 **Figure S 4-distributions of evolutionary model parameters.** Histograms of σ^2
 79 (evolutionary rate) and μ (directional parameter) for all traits in all model runs categorized
 80 by non-depositional, eolianite, and pedogenic phases of the sedimentary cycle.

81

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